

Spatiotemporal Gaussian Process Regression Advances Early Detection of Precipitation Emergence

Arjun Babu Nellikkattil¹, Megan Lickley^{1,2}, Mofan Zhang³, Sarah Fletcher^{3,4}

¹The Earth Commons, Georgetown University, Washington DC, USA

²Edmund A. Walsh School of Foreign Service, Georgetown University, Washington, DC, USA

³Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Stanford University, Stanford, CA, USA

⁴Woods Institute for the Environment, Stanford University, Stanford, CA, USA

Key Points:

- Three Bayesian approaches of increasing complexity are evaluated for their ability to estimate long-term precipitation changes and detect the emergence of new precipitation regimes.
- All Bayesian methods produce smaller prediction errors and narrower uncertainty ranges compared to traditional approaches.
- Among them, the Spatiotemporal Gaussian Process Regression performs best, accurately detecting the emergence of future precipitation changes earlier and across a wider range of locations.

Corresponding author: Arjun Nellikkattil, arjun.nellikkattil@georgetown.edu

Corresponding author: Megan Lickley, megan.lickley@georgetown.edu

Abstract

Detecting long-term precipitation trends is difficult because internal variability often obscures externally forced signals. Conventional methods, such as multimodel ensemble means (MMM), often suppress regional signals and overestimate future uncertainties. Here, we develop and compare Bayesian frameworks based on Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) that predict precipitation anomalies by combining observational records with priors derived from Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) Global Climate Models (GCMs). We test three variants: a univariate GPR (UGPR) using only temporal covariances, a circulation-aware GPR (CGPR) incorporating circulation variability, and a spatio-temporal GPR (SGPR) that exploits spatial and temporal covariances. Using leave-one-out cross-validation across 33 CMIP6 models conditioned on data up to 2020, we compare the predictive skill, uncertainty reduction, and signal emergence characteristics of all four approaches. All three GPR frameworks substantially outperform the CMIP6 MMM, reducing global predictive errors by approximately 60% and narrowing uncertainty by about 12%, with broadly comparable global-mean performance among the GPR methods. Differences between GPR variants emerge primarily at regional scales. In particular, SGPR advances the detection of forced precipitation changes by up to 15 years relative to UGPR in regions including the Middle East, Northwestern Africa, Eastern Europe, Japan, and parts of South America, while CGPR yields more limited and regionally heterogeneous improvements. These results demonstrate that while Bayesian GPR methods generally provide robust improvements over conventional ensemble approaches, explicitly accounting for spatiotemporal covariances advances the detection of precipitation signal emergence in selected regions. Our findings highlight the importance of regional covariance structure for early detection and underscore the value of flexible Bayesian frameworks for dynamically integrating observations into climate change detection and prediction.

Plain Language Summary

Identifying climate change impacts on precipitation is challenging because natural climate variability introduces substantial “noise” that obscures long-term climate trends. This makes it hard to know when long-term climate trends, such as shifts in precipitation, are actually emerging. Traditional approaches that average many climate model simulations often weaken the signal and overestimate uncertainty, delaying detection of new normals. In this study, we evaluate new statistical tools based on Gaussian Process Regression, a Bayesian machine learning approach that combines historical observations with Coupled Model Intercomparison Project outputs as prior information to improve predictions of future precipitation anomalies and associated uncertainties. We tested three versions: one using only past changes over time, one that also considers large-scale circulation patterns, and one that uses information across both space and time. Across 33 global climate models, all three Bayesian approaches produce similar overall improvements compared to traditional model averaging, reducing prediction errors by about 60% and narrowing uncertainty by about 12%. Differences between the methods mainly appear at regional scales. In particular, the approach that combines spatial and temporal information detects emerging changes in rainfall up to 15 years earlier than the simpler time-based method in regions such as the Middle East, parts of Africa, Eastern Europe, Japan, and South America. These findings show that while Bayesian machine learning methods generally improve predictions of future rainfall, explicitly accounting for how precipitation patterns vary across space can lead to earlier detection of climate change signals in some regions. This improved timing and regional detail can support earlier and more informed planning for climate adaptation.

1 Introduction

Evolving precipitation patterns represent one of the most pressing challenges for global water security, with far-reaching implications for agriculture, hydropower, and ecosystem stability (Jackson et al., 2001; Bano & Arshad, 2017; Conway et al., 2015; Baggio et al., 2021; Caretta et al., 2022). Recognizing this, the United Nations has highlighted the water-food-energy nexus as central to sustainable development (UN General Assembly, 2015; UN Secretariat, 2023), underscoring the urgent need for accurate predictions of future precipitation changes. Yet isolating the influence of climate change on precipitation remains difficult, as long-term anthropogenic trends are often obscured by natural variability (Lehner et al., 2020; Hawkins et al., 2020). While statistical methods have been applied to detect shifts in the distribution of climate variables, precipitation remains particularly challenging to characterize because of unresolved sub-grid processes, interactions with complex orography and its inherently high variability across spatial and temporal scales (Hawkins & Sutton, 2010; Martel et al., 2018; Williams et al., 2024). In contrast to surface temperature—where consistent warming trends are now evident worldwide (IPCC, 2021; Hawkins et al., 2020)—precipitation signals emerge more slowly and unevenly, complicating both detection and prediction. This uncertainty carries significant economic consequences, given that an estimated \$48 billion is invested annually in climate adaptation and water management (The World Bank, 2010). Improving methods to disentangle long-term precipitation trends from short-term variability is therefore essential for informing sustainable freshwater management, agricultural planning, and infrastructure resilience (Dessai et al., 2009; Swanson et al., 2010; M. Zhang et al., 2025).

The prevailing approach in climate science is to analyze ensembles of Global Climate Model (GCM) simulations from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) to estimate greenhouse gas emission driven changes in climate variables. These ensembles are typically averaged across models for each socio-economic scenarios, and initial conditions to highlight the externally forced signal while cancelling out the short-term variability (Knutti & Sedláček, 2012; Hawkins & Sutton, 2012). Although multimodel means provide valuable first-order insights, they can underestimate the true climate change signal and exaggerate confidence intervals especially when inter-model spread is large (D. M. Smith et al., 2019, 2020; Scaife & Smith, 2018). Moreover, assuming all GCMs are equally plausible ignores systematic biases and structural dependencies that reduce model independence (Knutti et al., 2017; Herger et al., 2018). Observational analyses suggest that certain models reproduce historical climate more faithfully, highlighting potential benefits of performance-based weighting. Recent studies embed this weighting into Bayesian frameworks, yielding improved uncertainty quantification and more robust probabilistic projections of precipitation (Tebaldi et al., 2005; R. L. Smith et al., 2009; Fan et al., 2017). For instance, Massoud et al. (2020) demonstrated that Bayesian Model Averaging (BMA) reduced uncertainty in U.S. precipitation projections by one-third while improving consistency with observations. These findings indicate that observationally informed weighting and Bayesian methods can substantially increase the reliability and practical utility of precipitation projections (Doss-Gollin & Keller, 2023).

Bayesian approaches also offer a key advantage by enabling continuous updates to probabilistic predictions as new observational data become available. This feature aligns with modern climate adaptation frameworks, which emphasize flexibility, robustness, and adaptive decision-making strategies that evolve with scientific advancements and emerging climate signals (Fletcher et al., 2023; Aall & Groven, 2022). Such approaches have been shown to reduce adaptation costs while effectively mitigating climate change impacts (Bloom, 2015; Kasprzyk et al., 2012; Willebrand et al., 2024; Skerker et al., 2023).

Building on this principle, Lickley and Fletcher (2024) developed a Bayesian framework that used a Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) to generate improved precipitation projections by integrating observational data with priors derived from CMIP5 sim-

119 ulations. Their framework was used to detect the Time of Emergence (ToE), defined as
 120 the first year in which the forced climate signal exceeds historical variability, marking
 121 when climate change effects become distinguishable from natural variability or “noise”
 122 (Giorgi & Bi, 2009; Mahlstein et al., 2012; J. Li et al., 2017). They further introduced
 123 the Time of Confidence (ToC), the earliest point when future precipitation signal can
 124 be correctly predicted, and defined the Advanced Warning Time (AWT) as the differ-
 125 ence between ToE and ToC. Using 1850-1950 as the baseline, their results showed that
 126 99% of the globe could exhibit emergence by century’s end, compared to 60% under con-
 127 ventional methods. However, they also found that in 34% of regions, emergence occurs
 128 without prior warning ($AWT \leq 0$), underscoring the limits of predictability in certain
 129 regions. In their study, posterior distributions were calculated by training the GPR model
 130 only on the temporal evolution of precipitation. It remains an open question whether
 131 accounting for circulation variability or spatio-temporal patterns could further strengthen
 132 predictive skill and allow for earlier detection of long-term precipitation changes.

133 In this study, we expand upon the Bayesian framework of Lickley and Fletcher (2024)
 134 to include circulation variability and spatiotemporal covariance structure to assess how
 135 these additional sources of information influence the prediction and emergence of long-
 136 term precipitation changes. Our approach integrates CMIP6 GCMs with observational
 137 data as they become available, enabling probabilistic projections of precipitation anoma-
 138 lies and earlier detection of externally forced signals. To advance beyond existing approaches,
 139 we introduce computational refinements and two methodological extensions: a circulation-
 140 aware GPR that conditions predictions on large-scale atmospheric variability in addi-
 141 tion to the temporal information (Section 3.3.2), and a spatio-temporal GPR that simul-
 142 taneously learns from spatial and temporal patterns of precipitation anomalies (Section 3.3.3).
 143 We evaluate the predictive skill of these GPR frameworks using a leave-one-out valida-
 144 tion approach, where one GCM is excluded from training and treated as pseudo-observations
 145 while the others are used for prediction (Section 4.1). Once validated, the framework is
 146 applied iteratively across all CMIP6 GCMs to estimate the projected mean precipita-
 147 tion change, its emergence, and the predictability of the emergence at each location (Sec-
 148 tion 4.2). Finally, we apply the framework using reanalysis datasets as observations, with
 149 CMIP6 precipitation as priors, to produce best-estimate projections of precipitation con-
 150 strained by actual observations (Section 4.3). Collectively, these advances clarify the re-
 151 gional value of incorporating circulation and spatiotemporal information in Bayesian de-
 152 tection frameworks and strengthen the foundation for anticipating water-related climate
 153 risks and informing adaptation planning.

154 2 Data

155 This study develops a data-driven Bayesian framework that combines long-term
 156 precipitation projections from climate models (Section 2.1) with near-term observational
 157 records (Section 2.2). The framework produces dynamically updatable forecasts of pre-
 158 cipitation change and identifies the emergence of precipitation anomalies.

159 2.1 CMIP6 Datasets

160 We use precipitation (TP) and mean sea level pressure (MSLP) from 33 CMIP6
 161 models, the latest multimodel ensemble of global climate simulations (Eyring et al., 2016).
 162 Two experiments are considered. Historical simulations (1850-2014), which represent past
 163 and present climate conditions. SSP5-8.5 scenario (2015-2100), which provides a high-
 164 emissions future trajectory (O’Neill et al., 2016). To isolate methodological differences,
 165 scenario uncertainty is excluded by restricting the analysis to a single Shared Socioeco-
 166 nomic Pathway (SSP), SSP5-8.5. The SSP5-8.5 was chosen to maximize the number of
 167 CMIP6 GCMs available for evaluation.

Together, these experiments provide continuous climate projections over the study period. The full list of models used is given in the Supplementary Table 1.

2.2 Reanalysis Data

To condition future projections with observational precipitation, we incorporate three global reanalysis products, each providing long-term, global data extending back to at least 1950. These include ERA5, produced by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), which spans 1940 to the present (Soci et al., 2024); JRA-3Q, developed by the Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA), available from September 1947 onward (Kosaka et al., 2024); and NCEP/NCAR, a joint product of the National Centers for Environmental Prediction and the National Center for Atmospheric Research, extending from 1948 to the present (Kalnay et al., 1996; Kistler et al., 2001).

These reanalysis datasets serve two complementary purposes. During model training, they anchor the Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) models to observational data, ensuring that the statistical relationships learned are grounded in reality. During prediction, they act as conditioning inputs, allowing the models to generate projections that reflect observations.

2.3 Preprocessing and Standardization

To ensure consistency across datasets, all fields are interpolated to a $5^\circ \times 5^\circ$ grid and aggregated to annual means. Annual mean precipitation at each grid point is standardized relative to the 1950-2000 baseline climatology. Specifically, for each dataset (CMIP6 GCM or reanalysis) g , year t , and location (λ, ϕ) , the standardized anomaly is:

$$\mathbf{p}_{annual}(g, t, \lambda, \phi) = \log\left(\frac{TP(g, t, \lambda, \phi) - \overline{TP}_H(g, \lambda, \phi)}{stddev(TP_H(g, \lambda, \phi))}\right) \quad (1)$$

Where \overline{TP}_H and σ_H are the mean and standard deviation of total precipitation during the baseline. These anomalies are then block-averaged to 5 year anomalies producing the final target variable $\mathbf{p}(t, \lambda, \phi)$ used in model fitting.

Two smoothed variants of \mathbf{p}_{annual} are also constructed and incorporated as priors in the GPR framework (see Section 3) to capture large-scale spatial and temporal trends. The variant denoted as \mathbf{p}^s represents a temporally smoothed field obtained using a 50-year running mean sampled every five years. The variant \mathbf{p}^{ss} further extends this approach by first applying a two-dimensional Gaussian spatial low-pass filter (as in May et al. (2022) with $n = 20$), followed by the same 50-year running mean. For the $5^\circ \times 5^\circ$ grid used here, the Gaussian filter replaces precipitation at each grid cell with a weighted average (based on the distance of each grid cell to the center cell) of neighboring values over a local spatial scale of approximately $15\text{-}20^\circ$ suppressing small-scale spatial variability while preserving coherent regional precipitation patterns. As a result, \mathbf{p}^{ss} captures both large-scale spatial structure and long-term temporal variability.

To minimize boundary artifacts introduced by smoothing, the rest of the analysis in this manuscript is restricted to the period 1950-2075 and to latitudes between 65°S and 65°N .

3 Methods

Our modeling approach develops and evaluates three GPR predictive frameworks alongside a conventional CMIP6 multimodel mean (MMM) baseline. We generate long-term projections of precipitation anomalies with each of the four methods, comparing how temporal, circulation-related, and spatiotemporal information influences predictive skill and emergence detection. In the following section, we describe our methods for model

validation (Section 3.1), we then introduce the MMM framework (Section 3.2) as well as each GPR specification (Section 3.3). Each of the four methods uses CMIP6 GCM ensemble and differ primarily in how information from the CMIP6 ensemble is used to calculate projected precipitation change and the uncertainty in the projection in response to greenhouse gas forcing. The CMIP6 MMM baseline, isolates the forced signal by averaging precipitation anomalies in RMs (Section 3.2) whereas the GPR frameworks use (\mathbf{p}^s) or spatiotemporally smoothed (\mathbf{p}^{ss}) precipitation anomalies from RMs to construct prior mean and covariance (Section 3.3) of the Bayesian regression framework. In Section 4.2 we present the time of confidence and time of emergence metrics, used for evaluating the efficacy of each method in predicting long term change.

3.1 Model Validation

Predicting long-term climate change is an inherently ill-posed problem: future conditions cannot be directly observed or validated. To address this limitation, we adopt a leave-one-out cross-validation (LOOCV) strategy using the CMIP6 ensemble of Global Climate Models (GCMs). In each iteration, standardized precipitation anomalies (\mathbf{p}) from one GCM is treated as pseudo-observations and designated as the held-out model (HOM). The remaining models (RMs) serve as the best available estimate of forced climate evolution and constitute the ensemble of models used for generating the mean and covariances which are then used in each of the GPR models. This iterative process is repeated until each of the 33 CMIP6 GCMs has served as the HOM, ensuring ensemble-wide robustness of the prediction method.

Each predictive model generates long-term projections of precipitation anomalies using a combination of the RMs. For the GPRs, a subset of the HOM is treated as pseudo observations and the remaining portion are treated as “future observations” or “target values”, not yet seen by the prediction model. These future observations are used for evaluating the predictive performance of the model. The predictive performance is quantified using complementary metrics that assess both accuracy and uncertainty calibration. The accuracy, assessed through the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) between the predicted and the pseudo-observed precipitation anomalies, quantifies how closely the model reproduces the target values. The second criterion measures the fraction of future observations that fall within the model’s posterior predictive intervals. For a well-calibrated probabilistic model, coverage should be consistent with Gaussian distribution (approximately 68% of observations within the 1σ predictive interval) with higher or lower values indicating overestimated or underestimated uncertainty, respectively.

3.2 CMIP6 Multimodel Mean (Baseline)

By averaging precipitation anomalies across the GCMs, the CMIP6 MMM aims to cancel out model-specific variability and yield a robust estimate of the externally forced signal (Tebaldi & Knutti, 2007; Knutti et al., 2010; Schaller et al., 2011). This approach remains one of the most widely used methods for estimating long-term climate change signals (Giorgi & Bi, 2009; Hawkins & Sutton, 2012; Doblas-Reyes et al., 2021).

Within the LOOCV setup, predictions for the HOM (black line in Figure 1a) are given by the mean of the temporally smoothed precipitation anomalies (\mathbf{p}^s) across the RMs (blue line in Figure 1a). Uncertainty in MMM projections is estimated as the square root of the sum of two independent components (blue shading in Figure 1a). The first component, inter-model variability, is represented by the standard deviation of the smoothed precipitation anomalies across the RMs (σ_{RM}^2), capturing differences among models in their simulated responses. The second component, internal variability, corresponds to the variance of the precipitation anomalies within the HOM during the historical baseline period of 1850-1950 (σ_{HOM}^2), reflecting the model’s intrinsic, unforced variability. Together, these components provide a comprehensive measure of uncertainty in the MMM-

262 based projections by combining the spread among models with the natural internal vari-
 263 ability of the climate system.

264 3.3 Gaussian Process Regression

265 Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) is a supervised machine learning method that
 266 models complex, nonlinear relationships without assuming a fixed functional form (Rasmussen
 267 & Williams, 2006; Wang, 2023). This non-parametric nature enables GPR to provide
 268 both predictions and associated measure of uncertainty, making it particularly useful for
 269 problems involving high variability and sparse training dataset such as precipitation pro-
 270 jections, sea level rise, tidal currents (Roberts et al., 2013; Hay et al., 2015; Sarkar et al.,
 271 2019; Paton & McNicholas, 2020).

272 A key strength of GPR is its Bayesian formulation: prior beliefs about the func-
 273 tion can be incorporated through the prior mean, choice of kernel and hyperparameters.
 274 As new observations become available (black lines in Figure 1b-e), GPR updates its pre-
 275 dictions (blue lines in Figure 1b-e) and uncertainty (blue shading in Figure 1b-e) by con-
 276 ditioning the prior distribution on the observed data. This property makes GPR ideal
 277 for adaptive frameworks, as posterior predictions can be iteratively updated with rela-
 278 tively small computational demands.

279 A Gaussian Process (GP) is fully defined by a mean function $m(x)$ and a covari-
 280 ance function (kernel) $k(x_i, x_j)$. Together, they specify a multivariate normal distribu-
 281 tion over precipitation anomalies \mathbf{p} given predictors \mathbf{X} :

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathbf{p}|\mathbf{X}) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{p}|\mu, \mathbf{K}) \quad (2)$$

282 Where $\mu = [m(\mathbf{x}_1), m(\mathbf{x}_1), \dots, m(\mathbf{x}_n)]$ is the prior mean vector and $K_{ij} = k(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j)$ is
 283 the covariance matrix.

284 Given observed precipitation changes (\mathbf{p}), GPR models the unobserved changes (\mathbf{p}^*)
 285 as a joint normal distribution:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p} \\ \mathbf{p}^* \end{bmatrix} = \mathcal{N} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \mu(\mathbf{X}) \\ \mu(\mathbf{X}^*) \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}) & K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}^*) \\ K(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{X}) & K(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{X}^*) \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (3)$$

286 From this, the posterior mean of the unobserved values, \mathbf{p}^* is:

$$\overline{\mathbf{p}^*} = \mu(\mathbf{X}^*) + \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{X})[\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X})]^{-1}(\mathbf{p} - \mu(\mathbf{X})) \quad (4)$$

287 and the posterior covariance is:

$$\text{cov}(\mathbf{p}) = \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{X}^*) - \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{X})[\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X})]^{-1}\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}^*) \quad (5)$$

288 The uncertainty in posterior predictions are calculated as the square root of the diag-
 289 onal elements of the covariance matrix (Equation (5)).

290 Our three different GPR variations differ in how the prior mean and covariance is
 291 defined, representing varying levels of statistical representation of the physical climate
 292 system (Table 1).

293 3.3.1 Univariate GPR (UGPR)

294 UGPR models the standardized long-term precipitation anomaly at each grid point,
 295 denoted \mathbf{p}^s , as a function of time conditioned on the “observed” anomalies, \mathbf{p} from HOM.
 296 The input vector \mathbf{X} consists of 5-year time steps from 1950-2075. The prior mean for each
 297 HOM represents the expected forced response and is set equal to the multimodel mean
 298 of RMs.

299 The UGPR kernel function encodes temporal correlations between precipitation
300 anomalies across time. It consists of three components:

$$k_g(t_i, t_j) = \underbrace{\mathcal{C}(t_i, t_j)}_1 + \underbrace{\sigma_t^2 \exp\left(-\frac{(t_i - t_j)^2}{2\ell_t^2}\right)}_2 + \underbrace{\sigma_w^2 I}_3 \quad (6)$$

301 Where, the first component captures the covariance of precipitation anomalies be-
302 tween times t_i and t_j as derived directly from GCM simulations. This term incorporates
303 prior physical knowledge of how precipitation covariances evolve through time, ensur-
304 ing that the GP model reflects realistic temporal behavior observed in climate simula-
305 tions. The second term, a squared exponential (SE) kernel, represents the smooth and
306 continuous evolution of precipitation anomalies over time. σ_t^2 determines the overall am-
307 plitude of variability, while the length scale, ℓ_t controls how rapidly correlations decay
308 as the time difference between observations increases. Large ℓ_t values indicate long-term
309 memory in the system, where anomalies remain correlated over extended periods, whereas
310 small values correspond to short-term fluctuations with rapidly decaying correlations.
311 The third component is a white-noise kernel that accounts for uncorrelated variability
312 not explained by the structured covariance terms, representing internal climate variabil-
313 ity and observational noise. Together, this additive kernel construction combines empir-
314 ically derived physical structure with flexible statistical smoothing, improving predic-
315 tive performance while maintaining a mathematically well-posed GP model (Lickley &
316 Fletcher, 2024; Agou et al., 2022; Bachoc et al., 2023).

317 Following Rasmussen and Williams (2006), the hyperparameters in the kernel are
318 optimized by maximizing the summed log-marginal likelihood for all HOMs at each lo-
319 cation for the training period. The summed marginal log likelihood (*SMLL*) for train-
320 ing period, \mathbf{t} , with $1950 \leq \mathbf{t} \leq 2000$ is given by

$$SMLL = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{g=k}^{n_{RM}+1} [\mathbf{p}_g(\mathbf{t}) - \mu_g(\mathbf{t})]^T \mathbf{K}_g^{-1}(\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{t}) [\mathbf{p}_g(\mathbf{t}) - \mu_g(\mathbf{t})] - \frac{1}{2} \log |\mathbf{K}_g| - \frac{n_t}{2} \log 2\pi \quad (7)$$

321 3.3.2 Circulation-aware GPR (CGPR)

322 CGPR extends UGPR by explicitly accounting for atmospheric circulation, which
323 can mask forced precipitation signals for decades (Lehner et al., 2017; Sippel et al., 2020,
324 2021). Local circulation is represented by the dominant variability mode $\mathbf{\Omega}$, derived from
325 the leading principal component of detrended *MSLP* within a $40^\circ \times 40^\circ$ window around
326 each grid cell. This provides a proxy for regional circulation patterns driven by large scale
327 climate oscillations.

328 As in UGPR, the prior mean is given by the multimodel mean of precipitation anoma-
329 lies from RMs. The covariance function now depends on both time, t_i and the correspond-
330 ing mode of circulation Ω_i , through $\mathbf{x}_i = [t_i, \Omega_i]$:

$$\mathbf{k}_g(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j) = \mathcal{C}(t_i, t_j) + \sigma_t^2 \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j)^T \mathbf{\Lambda}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j)\right) + \sigma_w^2 I \quad (8)$$

331 The length scale matrix is defined as:

$$\mathbf{\Lambda} = \begin{bmatrix} \ell_t^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \ell_\Omega^2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (9)$$

332 With ℓ_t controlling temporal correlations and ℓ_Ω controlling sensitivity to circu-
333 lation variability. Larger ℓ_Ω implies weaker dependence on circulation, while smaller val-
334 ues mean precipitation is strongly conditioned on circulation states. The \mathcal{C} term repre-
335 sents correlations in p^s across RMs, as in UGPR. The anisotropic SE kernel allows pre-
336 cipitation anomalies to be similar either when years are close in time or when they share

337 similar circulation regimes. Hyperparameters $(\ell_t, \ell_\Omega, \sigma_t^2)$ are optimized by maximizing
 338 the log marginal likelihood (Equation (7)).

339 During training, Ω is derived from historical *MSLP* in the HOM, capturing the
 340 observed variability explained by circulation anomalies. For future projections, Ω is set
 341 to its mean, zero, as we do not have circulation anomaly predictions of the future. This
 342 effectively removes circulation-driven noise from future prediction uncertainties while pre-
 343 serving the forced trend. In effect, CGPR learns the degree to which circulation has mod-
 344 ulated precipitation and masked the forced trend historically, then filters it out of pre-
 345 cipitation when projecting the forced trend forward.

346 **3.3.3 Spatiotemporal GPR (SGPR)**

347 SGPR further expands the UGPR framework by incorporating both spatial and
 348 temporal dependencies. Many regions exhibit coherent precipitation responses to large-
 349 scale modes (e.g., ENSO, monsoons) (Fischer et al., 2014; Deza et al., 2014). Moreover,
 350 shifts in large-scale circulation patterns may cause precipitation changes to appear in
 351 surrounding regions before they emerge at the central grid point.

352 This spatiotemporal formulation allows the model to learn relationships between
 353 short-term precipitation anomalies at nearby locations and their associated long-term
 354 trends (Zhao et al., 2020; Kleiber et al., 2012; J. Zhang et al., 2023; Z. Li et al., 2025).
 355 As a result, SGPR is particularly effective in reducing prediction noise and enhancing
 356 performance in regions where local variability is high but the broader climate signal ex-
 357 hibits large-scale coherence.

358 To incorporate spatial context without incurring prohibitive computational costs
 359 (which scale as $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$ in GPR), we define a Significantly Correlated Neighborhood (SCN)
 360 for each target grid point. The SCN comprises a subset of surrounding locations that
 361 consistently exhibit statistically significant correlations with the long-term precipitation
 362 anomalies at the target location. This approach reduces dimensionality while retaining
 363 the most informative spatial relationships. For each target location, a $35^\circ \times 35^\circ$ search
 364 window is used to calculate correlations across all RMs between \mathbf{p}^s at the target loca-
 365 tion in 2075, the last year in our analysis, and the corresponding values within the win-
 366 dow for all time steps. Approximately ten grid points showing significant correlations
 367 (p value ≤ 0.1) across the most time steps are selected to form the SCN inputs for the
 368 SGPR model.

369 The prior mean is defined as the multimodel mean of RMs as a function of both
 370 space and time. The spatiotemporal covariance kernel combines temporal and spatial
 371 components as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 k_g(\mathbf{X}_i, \mathbf{X}_j) = & \underbrace{\mathcal{C}_t(t_i, t_j) + \sigma_t^2 \exp\left(-\frac{(t_i - t_j)^2}{2\ell_t^2}\right)}_{\text{Temporal Kernel}} + \\
 & \underbrace{\sigma_s \left[\mathcal{C}_s(\mathbf{s}_i, \mathbf{s}_j) + \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{s}_i - \mathbf{s}_j)^T \Lambda^{-1}(\mathbf{s}_i - \mathbf{s}_j)\right) \right]}_{\text{Spatial Kernel}} + \sigma_w^2 I \quad (10)
 \end{aligned}$$

372 Where, each observation is represented as $\mathbf{X}_i = (t_i, \mathbf{s}_i)$, with $\mathbf{s}_i = (\lambda_i, \phi_i)$ de-
 373 noting the spatial coordinates (longitude, latitude) of the i^{th} observation.

374 The empirical covariance function, $\mathcal{C}_t(t_i, t_j)$ captures the inter-model temporal co-
 375 variance. It equals $\mathcal{C}_t(t_i, t_j)$ when the two observations share the same spatial location
 376 ($\Delta s = 0$), and 0 otherwise. The SE kernel in the temporal kernel encodes temporal co-

377 variance between short-term anomalies and long-term climate signals, with variance σ_t^2
 378 and characteristic length scale ℓ_t .

379 The empirical spatial covariance term, $\mathcal{C}_s(\mathbf{s}_i, \mathbf{s}_j)$ encodes inter-model spatial covari-
 380 ance. It equals $\mathcal{C}_s(\mathbf{s}_i, \mathbf{s}_j)$ when $\Delta s = 0$; 0 otherwise. Similar to \mathcal{C}_t , it reflects prior
 381 beliefs about spatial coherence in precipitation anomalies. An anisotropic SE kernel rep-
 382 represents spatial covariance between near-term and long-term anomalies, with distinct length
 383 scales along longitude and latitude ℓ_λ and ℓ_ϕ and a variance σ_s^2 . The variance is constrained
 384 to $0 \leq \sigma_s^2 \leq 1$ to prevent overfitting. The White noise term, $(\sigma_w^2 I)$ accounts for resid-
 385 ual variability.

386 As in UGPR and CGPR, kernel hyperparameters are optimized by maximizing the
 387 summed log-marginal likelihood for the training period (Equation (7)).

Table 1. Comparison of the three GPR Models, showing how prior information is fed into the three different frameworks.

Component	UGPR	CGPR	SGPR
Inputs	Time (t)	Time (t), Dominant Circulation Mode (Ω)	Time (t), Longitude (λ), Latitude (ϕ)
Prior Mean	Multi-model mean of RMs standardized precipitation anomalies	Same as UGPR	Multi-model mean of RMs standardized precipitation anomalies as a function of time and space
Kernel Components	SE(t) + Empirical GCM Covariance + White Noise	Anisotropic SE(t, Ω) + Empirical GCM Covariance + White Noise	SE(t) + Empirical GCM Temporal Covariance + Anisotropic SE (λ, ϕ) + Empirical GCM Spatial Covariance + White Noise
Computational Considerations	Efficient (Univariate per location)	Moderate (Adds Ω)	High (SCN-based subset to reduce cost)

388 3.4 Detection and Prediction of Emergence

389 A core objective of this study is to improve early detection of long-term change,
 390 which we have defined here to be when precipitation at each location becomes signifi-
 391 cantly different from its historical mean. To quantify both the timing of detection and
 392 the ability to anticipate future change, we use three complementary metrics: the Time
 393 of Emergence (ToE), Time of Confidence (ToC), and the Emergence Lead Time (ELT).
 394 Together, these metrics distinguish between when a climate signal is detectable in hind-
 395 sight (ToE), when its future emergence can be confidently predicted (ToC), and how much
 396 advance warning is provided by the prediction system (ELT).

397 ToE describes when a forced precipitation signal becomes statistically significant
 398 from background variability (Hawkins & Sutton, 2012; Giorgi & Bi, 2009). Formally, we
 399 define ToE as the earliest year t in which two conditions are satisfied simultaneously: the

Figure 1. Detection and prediction of climate signal emergence. (a) CMIP6 MMM posterior predictions for a held-out-model (HOM), showing the multimodel mean of the RMs (blue) and associated $\pm 1\sigma$ uncertainty (blue shading), with HOM precipitation anomalies (black). (b)-(e) Spatiotemporal Gaussian Process Regression (SGPR) predictions illustrating Bayesian updating as new observations (solid black) become available, with future anomalies shown as dashed black. The posterior mean (blue) and $\pm 1\sigma$ confidence intervals (blue shaded) are recalculated at each step. (d) Time of Confidence (ToC ; green dashed) and the predicted Time of Emergence (ToE^p ; red dashed) based on data up to ToC . (e) Actual ToE (red dashed) using the full record and the resulting Emergence Lead Time (ELT ; yellow shading) between ToC and ToE

400 projected long-term precipitation mean has changed by at least 1-sigma for more than
 401 90% of subsequent years $t' > t$, and the emergence condition is satisfied in the final year
 402 (2075) as well as at least one additional earlier time step (vertical dotted red line in Fig-
 403 ure 1d, e). While the ToE identifies emergence in hindsight (vertical dotted red line in Fig-
 404 ure 1e), the Time of Confidence (ToC) measures when emergence can be confidently

405 predicted in advance. For the CMIP6 MMM, predictions are fixed once the GCM sim-
 406 ulations are released; thus, the ToC effectively corresponds to the release year. In this
 407 setup, each location is either projected to show emergence or not, with no updates once
 408 fixed. In contrast, under the GPR framework, the ToC is defined as the first year when
 409 the posterior mean predicts emergence (vertical dotted green line in Figure 1d). This es-
 410 timate serves as the predicted ToE (ToE^p) (vertical dotted red line in Figure 1d). Us-
 411 ing the full dataset spanning 1950-2075, we can also evaluate the actual ToE (Figure 1e).

412 ELT quantifies the advance warning provided by the prediction system and is de-
 413 fined as the difference between the actual ToE and the ToC (yellow shading in Figure 1e).
 414 Positive ELT values indicate that emergence is anticipated before it occurs, while neg-
 415 ative values indicate delayed detection after emergence has already taken place. ELT there-
 416 fore provides a direct measure of the usefulness of a prediction framework for enabling
 417 early planning and adaptation to changing precipitation regimes.

418 4 Results

419 We present the results in three parts. First, we evaluate the predictive performance
 420 of the proposed GPR frameworks relative to the CMIP6 MMM baseline. Second, we an-
 421 alyze the emergence of climate change signals by computing the ToE, ToC, and the as-
 422 sociated ELT. We also investigate how adding additional variables like circulation and
 423 spatial variability affect the performance of GPR based frameworks compared to UGPR.
 424 Finally, we generate long-term precipitation anomaly projections conditioned on reanal-
 425 ysis datasets, providing our best estimate of future changes. In the first two analyzes,
 426 precipitation anomalies from each HOM are treated as target pseudo-observations, while
 427 the prior mean and covariance are derived from the RMs. In the final analysis, the re-
 428 analysis datasets serve as observations, with CMIP6 anomalies used solely to construct
 429 the prior. The first two parts validate the predictive skill of the frameworks, while the
 430 third delivers projections conditioned on observed data providing our best estimate of
 431 future projections to date.

432 4.1 Validation of the frameworks

433 We begin by evaluating the predictive accuracy of the GPR frameworks using a hindcast-
 434 style validation experiment. Posterior forecasts for \mathbf{p}^s were generated for each HOM us-
 435 ing precipitation anomalies up to 2020 as input. The posterior means at each grid cell
 436 were then compared against the HOM's true long-term anomalies, and performance was
 437 measured using RMSE. All Bayesian frameworks substantially outperformed the CMIP6
 438 MMM baseline, reducing prediction errors globally by 60% (Figure 2). While the mag-
 439 nitude of error varies, their spatial distribution closely follows the variance of standard-
 440 ized precipitation anomalies, reflecting the influence of inter-model spread (Supplemen-
 441 tary Figure 1). Among the GPR methods, the SGPR achieved the lowest RMSE values
 442 across most regions (stippling in Figure 2d). However, the improvement of SGPR over
 443 the simpler UGPR was rarely statistically significant. This suggests that most of the pre-
 444 dictive skill comes from the basic UGPR approach, while including circulation variabil-
 445 ity (CGPR) or spatial dependencies (SGPR) provides only marginal benefits. These find-
 446 ings hold even when we change the observational period, whether shortened to 2000 (Sup-
 447plementary Figure 2) or extended to 2040 (Supplementary Figure 3). All methods pro-
 448 duced well-calibrated confidence intervals, capturing, on average 68% of the posterior
 449 variability (Supplementary Figure 4). GPR methods yielded distributions more tightly
 450 centered on the target of 0.68 compared to the MMM, while also narrowing interval widths
 451 globally by $\approx 12\%$.

Figure 2. Multimodel mean RMSE in posterior predictions using data up to 2020 as observations for (a) CMIP6 MMM, (b) UGPR, (c) CGPR, and (d) SGPR. Black stippling in (b-d) indicates the method with the lowest RMSE at a given grid cell; red stippling marks locations where the method achieves significantly lower errors than UGPR.

Figure 3. Fraction of global area with correct (green), incorrect (red), and no emergence (gray). Results are shown for (a) CMIP6 MMM and (b-d) UGPR conditioned on pseudo-observations up to 2000, 2050, and 2070.

4.2 Emergence of Climate Change Signals and Emergence Lead Time

We next examined when and where externally forced precipitation signals become detectable above natural variability. The GPR frameworks offer an advantage here because they update posterior predictions as new data are assimilated, allowing emergences to be tracked progressively. By contrast, the CMIP6 MMM produces a single fixed prediction per location, with the ToC effectively tied to the model release year (2019) whenever emergence is detected. This key difference allows GPR methods to adapt their predictions over time, aligning more closely with evolving “observations” and enabling more widespread and accurate detection of emergence compared to the static CMIP6 MMM baseline.

Across 33 CMIP6 GCMs, on average, CMIP6 MMM correctly identifies emergence in only 35% of the global area (Figure 3a). In comparison, the SGPR improves this detection rate to 44% using data up to 2020, 53% by 2050, and 60% by 2070 (Figure 3b-d). GPR methods also generate fewer false emergences, with error rates declining steadily as more observations are assimilated. Comparable improvements are seen for UGPR and CGPR (Supplementary Figure. 5, Supplementary Figure. 6). These findings demonstrate that GPR frameworks not only detect more emergences but also refine predictions as information accumulates.

We further examine the spatial structure of predictability using the median ToC across CMIP6 models (Figure 4). Polar regions and subtropical highs show the earliest emergence, while storm track boundaries emerge later-consistent with known precipitation patterns (Giorgi & Bi, 2009; Rojas et al., 2019; Lickley & Fletcher, 2024). Overall, UGPR detects earlier ToC than the CMIP6 multi-model mean, in part because it reduces uncertainty by conditioning posteriors on “observations”. Among the GPR variants, SGPR yields the clearest improvement, detecting significantly earlier ToC than UGPR in regions such as the Middle East, northwestern Africa, Eastern Europe, Japan, and parts of South America (Figure 4c). CGPR also improves emergence prediction regionally, but its gains are rarely statistically significant (Figure 4b). These advances show that Bayesian methods extend the time available to anticipate precipitation shifts. Note, however, that the emergence prediction is also delayed in some locations (red shading in Figure 4b, c).

Across the globe, GPR frameworks deliver positive ELTs more often than CMIP6 MMM, providing earlier warnings of precipitation regime shifts. Among the GPR frameworks, SGPR improves the early predictability of precipitation emergence in many of the same locations where it gives an earlier ToC (Figure 5d). However, ELT must be interpreted carefully. Because GPR frameworks often predict both earlier ToE and earlier ToC,

Figure 4. Median time of confidence (ToC) across models. (a) ToC from UGPR; hatched regions indicate locations where fewer than half the models agree on the direction of emergence. Differences in median ToC for (b) CGPR and (c) SGPR relative to UGPR, with stippling marking regions of statistically significant differences. Significance calculated at 95% level using the two-sided Wilcoxon signed-rank test (Wilcoxon, 1945).

487 the lead time does not always increase, even when the overall detection skill improves.
 488 In many regions—such as Eastern Europe and the Middle East—earlier ToC from SGPR
 489 translates into longer ELT, providing valuable early warning (Figure 5d). However, this
 490 relationship is not universal: for example, CGPR shows earlier ToC off the California
 491 coast, but ToE also shifts earlier, resulting in minimal net gain (Figure 5c). Therefore,
 492 ToC rather than ToE is used to evaluate the GPR framework’s ability to predict pre-
 493 cipitation emergence. Overall, SGPR provides the most consistent improvements in ToC
 494 and ELT relative to UGPR, while CGPR offers little. As expected, regions dominated
 495 by internal variability, such as midlatitude storm tracks, remain difficult to predict: here,
 496 large inter-model variance produces negative ELTs, meaning emergence is only confirmed

Figure 5. Emergence Lead Time (ELT) across methods. ELT from (a) CMIP6 MMM, (b) UGPR. Differences in ELT for (c) CGPR and (d) SGPR relative to UGPR.

497 after it has occurred. Even so, ToC estimates remain useful in practice, since real-world
 498 detection requires sufficient observational data after a signal physically emerges.

499 **4.3 Longterm Precipitation anomalies conditioned on reanalysis**

Figure 6. Predicted mean change in precipitation in 2075 using SGPR conditioned on observations up to 2020. (a) HOM-based predictions from CMIP6 models, averaged across 33 HOMs; (b) predictions from reanalysis datasets, averaged across three reanalysis products; (c-d) differences relative to the CMIP6 multi-model mean. Hatched areas indicate regions where fewer than half of the models agree on the sign of emergence. For visual clarity, regions with smaller than 1 mm/day annual mean precipitation is masked out.

500 We demonstrate the practical utility of the Bayesian framework by generating precipi-
 501 tation projections conditioned on real-world observational datasets. We focus on re-
 502 sults from SGPR, as it consistently outperforms other GPR variants in predictive ac-
 503 curacy, uncertainty quantification, and early emergence detection. This application high-
 504 lights the ability of the SGPR framework to integrate observations and CMIP6 simu-

505 lations into improved, probabilistic estimates of long-term precipitation change and its
 506 emergence, strengthening its value for climate monitoring and adaptation planning.

507 Projections for 2075 were generated using two types of observational proxies: HOMs
 508 from the CMIP6 ensemble (Figure 6a) and reanalysis datasets (Figure 6b), both con-
 509 ditioned on data through 2020. For HOM-based projections, priors were constructed from
 510 RMs, whereas for reanalysis-based projections, priors were derived from the full CMIP6
 511 ensemble. Predictions from each proxy were then averaged to obtain the mean precip-
 512 itation change. Both approaches yield broadly consistent spatial patterns, though mag-
 513 nitudes differ. HOM-based predictions show smaller anomalies, partly reflecting the larger
 514 ensemble size (33 models vs. 3 reanalyses), which damps variability. As a result, fewer
 515 grid points display consistent emergence in the reanalysis-based projections. Still, regions
 516 where HOMs and reanalyses agree provide higher confidence in robust future changes.

517 Reanalysis based predictions deviate more strongly from CMIP6 means in regions
 518 of complex topography, such as the Andes and Himalayas, underscoring the limitations
 519 of coarse GCM resolution in representing orographic precipitation. Over Central Africa,
 520 HOMs and CMIP6 GCMs project wetter conditions, while reanalyses suggest drying. Sim-
 521 ilarly, in Eastern Europe and Russia, reanalyses predict drying whereas CMIP6 mod-
 522 els project wetting. Despite these differences, both approaches consistently indicate a
 523 strengthening of the South Asian monsoon (Sharma et al., 2025) and a northward shift
 524 of midlatitude storm tracks (Nellikattil et al., 2023; Bengtsson et al., 2006). These re-
 525 sults demonstrate the value of integrating observations with models in a Bayesian frame-
 526 work, refining projections while also highlighting regions of persistent uncertainty.

527 **5 Conclusions and Further Discussions**

528 In this study, we extend the Bayesian framework of Lickley and Fletcher (2024) to
 529 evaluate how different GPR structures influence the prediction and emergence of long-
 530 term precipitation change. Using HOMs as pseudo-observations and RMs to construct
 531 priors, we demonstrated that GPR produces more accurate predictions and enables ear-
 532 lier and more widespread detection of precipitation emergence compared to the CMIP6
 533 multimodel mean. Among the variants, UGPR provides strong overall performance with
 534 minimal computational requirements, while the inclusion of dominant circulation modes
 535 (CGPR) adds little significant global skill. These findings suggest that while circulation
 536 variability is valuable for subseasonal-to-seasonal prediction, it adds limited skill for long-
 537 term climate anomalies. By contrast, SGPR reduces prediction errors and advances the
 538 ToC in many regions suggesting coherent spatial patterns are an indicator for long-term
 539 climate change signals. GPR-based predictions conditioned on reanalysis data also cap-
 540 ture large-scale CMIP6-projected features-such as subtropical drying, poleward storm-
 541 track shifts, and strengthening Indian monsoons, while revealing discrepancies in Cen-
 542 tral Africa, Western Russia, and orographically complex regions. In summary, GPR frame-
 543 works deliver more accurate predictions and better-calibrated uncertainties than the CMIP6
 544 MMM. Accurate predictions combined with narrower uncertainty intervals allows GPR
 545 frameworks to correctly identify the emergence of climate signals earlier than CMIP6 MMM.
 546 Advanced variants like SGPR offer improved projections and uncertainty quantification
 547 compared to UGPR resulting in the earlier detection of precipitation emergences in many
 548 regions.

549 Compared to Lickley and Fletcher (2024), our study benefited from computational
 550 refinements but also encountered important data constraints. While their CMIP5 anal-
 551 ysis drew on 16 models with outputs spanning 1850-2300, only six CMIP6 GCMs pro-
 552 vide simulations beyond 2100, limiting our prediction horizon to 2075. Furthermore, spa-
 553 tiotemporal GPR requires globally gridded datasets (covering both land and ocean), re-
 554 stricting our training period to post-1950 when such coverage became available. Whereas,
 555 Lickley and Fletcher (2024) used the land precipitation data from Climate Research Unit

556 (CRU) starting from 1900. Consequently, our baseline climatology (1950-2000) is later
 557 than that of Lickley and Fletcher (2024) (1870-1970), potentially delaying emergence sig-
 558 nals in our framework.

559 Finally, while the framework was applied here at coarse spatial and temporal scales,
 560 the SGPR design is general and can be adapted to higher resolutions. This opens op-
 561 portunities for statistical downscaling of precipitation projections, integration with hy-
 562 drological impact models, and development of adaptive early-warning systems. By bridg-
 563 ing models and observations within a Bayesian learning framework, this work provides
 564 a flexible foundation for anticipating hydrological risks and supporting evidence-based
 565 climate adaptation.

566 **AI Transparency Statement**

567 Portions of this manuscript benefited from the use of generative AI tools (OpenAI's
 568 ChatGPT, GPT-4,5). These tools were employed to assist with language refinement, re-
 569 structuring for clarity, and improving readability. All scientific content, analyses, results,
 570 and interpretations were conceived, conducted, and validated exclusively by the authors.
 571 The authors carefully reviewed and edited any AI-assisted text to ensure accuracy, orig-
 572 inality, and compliance with scientific standards.

573 **Open Research Section**

574 All code and processed data necessary to reproduce the figures in this manuscript
 575 are available in the Zenodo repository. Raw CMIP6 model output can be accessed via
 576 the Earth System Grid Federation and is stored on Google Cloud.

577 **Conflict of Interest disclosure**

578 The author declares that there are no conflicts of interest relevant to this work.

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